

A FLEXIBLE 3D FEA MODELLING APPROACH FOR PREDICTING THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF PLAIN WEAVE UNIT CELL

P. Tan, L. Tong and G. P. Steven

*Department of Aeronautical Engineering, University of Sydney, NSW 2006 Australia
Cooperative Research Center for Aerospace Structures, P.O.Box 30, 351 Milperra Road,
Bankstown, NSW 2200, Australia.*

SUMMARY: A finite element analysis (FEA) modelling approach was developed for predicting the mechanical properties of plain weave graphite/epoxy fabric-reinforced composites. 3D FEA models for a single layer plain weave fabric were generated by interfacing an in-house computer code with the FEA software Strand6 using 8-node brick and 6-node wedge elements. The paths of the impregnated tow (or yarn) within the composite materials were chosen to be sinusoidal, and a lenticular cross-section formed by two sinusoidal curves was utilised in the models. Pure tension and shear loading were applied. Results from FEA models were in good agreement with the present test results and those reported in the literature. In addition, a parametric study illustrated the effects of the geometrical dimensions of a unit cell on its mechanical properties.

KEYWORDS: woven fabric-reinforced composite, mechanical properties, finite element analysis (FEA) model

INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced woven fabric has been widely adopted in aerospace structures. To effectively utilise this material, it is necessary to evaluate its mechanical properties for a wide range of weave architecture parameters and to tailor the composite to the specified requirements of its role in practical structures [2]. Measurements of these properties are difficult and can be very expensive when investigating the effects of some manufacturing and geometrical parameters. Fortunately, theoretical and FEA modelling provide a cost-effective alternative for determining these properties. However, modelling the architecture of woven fabric-reinforced composite material in detail is difficult. Part of this difficulty is due to the complicated architecture of the woven fabric composite materials when viewed at the same scale as the weave geometry [3]. Hence, most of research workers developed the models based on the simplified geometry of woven fabric composites. Earlier work was carried out by Ishakawa and Chou [4-7] who developed one-dimensional models for woven fabric-reinforced composites. Later, various analytical and FEA models for predicting the mechanical properties of woven fabrics were proposed and developed, including the one-dimensional models [8]; two-dimensional models [9-11] and three-dimensional models [12-15].

In this study a flexible 3D FEA modelling approach is proposed for determining the mechanical properties of plain weave fabric-reinforced composite materials. The models created are capable of producing a 3D representation and visualisation of any plain weave unit

cell. The approach was validated by comparing with the test results. In addition, a parametric study was conducted to investigate the effects of geometric dimensions of a unit cell on its mechanical properties.

DEVELOPMENT OF FEA MODEL FOR A PLAIN WEAVE UNIT CELL

When developing the computer model of a plain weave unit cell, it is predefined that the model should be general and capable of further development and refinements. Thus, a general model, capable of producing any required weave geometry, and not restricted to any particular geometry or to a particular textile description, is required. For easy construction of any plain weave unit cell model, a flexible modelling approach is necessary. In addition, in order to evaluate the mechanical behaviour, a representation of a plain weave which is suitable for finite element meshing and analysis is required [2]. In this section, the details of the geometry for a woven fabric unit cell, the boundary conditions and loadings chosen will be discussed. The procedure for developing the 3D FEA models and the relevant assumptions will be described.

Fig. 1: 3D FEA model for plain weave unit cell

Fig. 2: Photomicrograph of a section of T300/934 plane weave laminate

Geometry and Assumptions for Plain Weave Unit Cell

Due to the complicated architecture of woven fabrics, it is difficult to describe the 3D unit cell geometry at the same scale as the woven fabric micro geometry. Hence, the geometrical model for a plain weave unit cell was established at the yarn level. Each yarn contains a few thousand fibres, and all fibres in each yarn are assumed to follow the same path which is

chosen to be sinusoidal. Also, a strictly lenticular cross-section formed by two sinusoidal curves is utilised in the model (see Fig. 1(a) with resin and (b) removing the resin from the model). The 3D FEA models are easy to be created by interfacing an in-house computer code with the FEA software Strand6 [1]. These models include some of the major parameters affecting the mechanical properties of composite, ie. impregnated yarn orientation, fibre volume fraction, mechanical properties of composite constituents. They can be evaluated from the scan of real weave fabric geometry (see Fig. 2), which was obtained by using an image analysis system together with the Iphoto Plus software. The mechanical properties for the composite constituents in a plain weave unit cell are considered to be homogeneous and isotropic for the resin but orthotropic for the impregnated fibre yarns with the respect to the principle material axis (or local coordinate system).

Boundary Conditions and Loadings

To evaluate the stiffness constants for a plain weave unit cell, six separate strain vectors are respectively applied to the relevant unit cell model using the Lagrange Multipliers Method. Six separate FEA cases need to be run respectively on the same FEA model for the corresponding six separate strain vectors ($\epsilon_x=0.001$, $\epsilon_y=0.001$, $\epsilon_z=0.001$, $\gamma_{xy}=0.001$, $\gamma_{yz}=0.001$, $\gamma_{zx}=0.001$), and the relevant boundary conditions for each case are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Boundary conditions for cases (a)-(f)

Case	Boundary conditions
a	$DX _{x=l_x}=0.001l_x, DX _{x=0}=0, DY _{y=0}=DY _{y=l_y}=0, DZ _{z=0}=DZ _{z=l_z}=0$
b	$DY _{y=l_y}=0.001l_y, DY _{y=0}=0, DX _{x=0}=DX _{x=l_x}=0, DZ _{z=0}=DZ _{z=l_z}=0$
c	$DZ _{z=l_z}=0.001l_z, DZ _{z=0}=0, DX _{x=0}=DX _{x=l_x}=0, DY _{y=0}=DY _{y=l_y}=0$
d	$DX _{y=l_y}=0.0005l_y, DX _{y=0}=0, DY _{x=l_x}=0.0005l_x, DY _{x=0}=0, DZ _{z=0}=DZ _{z=l_z}=0$
e	$DY _{z=l_z}=0.0005l_z, DY _{z=0}=0, DZ _{y=l_y}=0.0005l_y, DZ _{y=0}=0, DX _{x=0}=DX _{x=l_x}=0,$
f	$DX _{z=l_z}=0.0005l_z, DX _{z=0}=0, DY _{y=0}=DY _{y=l_y}=0, DZ _{x=l_x}=0.0005l_x, DZ _{x=0}=0$

Considering the boundary conditions and strain vectors selected above, the required mechanical properties can be evaluated from the relevant equations [16].

EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

In order to investigate the validity of the developed FEA models, 18 tests were carried out. The specimen preparation, testing procedure, experimental results and comparisons between the predicted and testing results are discussed in this section.

Specimen Preparation and Testing Procedure

In this experimental investigation, plain weave graphic/epoxy fabric reinforced composite materials T300/934 (3K-70-PW) were used.

Eight layers (or plies) of prepreg woven fabrics were laminated. The stacking sequence of laminate specimens is balanced and symmetric so that the bending coupling stiffness and shear coupling stiffness terms are zero, and the torsion coupling stiffness is relatively low;

close to their minimum due to the fine ply distribution [19]. The lay-up sequence and the thickness of the laminate specimens are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Lay-up sequence and thickness of laminate specimens

Specimen group	Stack sequence	Thickness of laminates (mm)	Purpose	Number of specimens
A	$[0]_8$	1.75	Test for E_1, ν_{12}	6
B	$[90]_8$	1.75	Test for E_2, ν_{12}	6
C	$[+45/-45]_{4s}$	1.75	Test for G_{12}	6

Fig. 3: Autoclave curve cycle

Fig. 4: The geometry of test specimen

All specimens were laminated from prepreg plain weave fabric sheets and cured in an autoclave following a curing cycle shown in Fig. 3 [20]. The configuration of the specimens is in accordance with the ASTM D 3039-76 and is shown in Fig. 4 [19, 21-23]. Strain gauges with $120 \pm 0.3 \Omega$ gauge resistance and $2.13 \pm 1\%$ gauges factor were located at the mid length of a specimen. These strain gauges can be used for measuring the strains in both longitudinal

and transverse directions. Static tension tests were performed by Instron machine. The specimens were tested at a room temperature (26°C) and at a cross-head speed of 1mm/min. Two computer data acquisition systems were used in the test for collecting the relevant data, eg., the loading, displacement and the strains. These two systems were driven by the software packages Instron Merlin and Labview respectively, which were operated via an user interface menu.

The geometrical parameters for a plain weave unit cell interested were obtained from the photomicrograph of a specimen section and listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Geometrical dimensions and fibre volume fraction

models	l_x (mm)	l_y (mm)	l_z (mm)	V_f^o (%)
ModEXP	2.1	2.1	0.22	50.1

The overall fibre volume fraction V_f^o was evaluated using the following equation

$$V_f^o = \frac{N \times \rho_A}{T \times D} \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of ply for the laminate specimen, ρ_A is fibre areal weight (g/m²), D is fibre density (g/cc) and T is the thickness of laminate specimen [24].

Table 4 lists the mechanical properties for the T300 carbon fibre and the 934 resin epoxy as well as the mechanical properties for the impregnated tow (T300/934) that were calculated using the following micromechanics equations proposed by Chamis [18]

$$E_{11} = V_f' \times E_{1f} + V_m' \times E_m \quad (2)$$

$$E_{22} = E_{33} = \frac{E_m}{1 - \sqrt{V_f'} \times (1 - E_m / E_{2f})} \quad (3)$$

$$G_{12} = G_{31} = \frac{G_m}{1 - \sqrt{V_f'} \times (1 - G_m / G_{12f})} \quad (4)$$

$$G_{23} = \frac{G_m}{1 - \sqrt{V_f'} \times (1 - G_m / G_{23f})} \quad (5)$$

$$v_{12} = v_{13} = V_f' \times v_{12f} + V_m' \times v_m \quad (6)$$

$$v_{23} = \frac{E_{22}}{2 \times G_{23}} \quad (7)$$

Using the data given in Table 4, the mechanical properties for a T300/934 plain weave unit cell were predicted with the aid of the relevant 3D FEA models and are tabulated in Table 5. The predicted values are compared with those reported by the Boeing company [25], and the present experimental results which were obtained following the ASTM test standards ASTM D 3096-76 and ASTM D3518-76.

In Table 5, the differences between the predicted and experimental results are 4.9% for the in-plane Young's moduli E_1 and E_2 , 12.2% for the in-plane Poisson's ratio v_{12} and 1.7% for the in-plane shear modulus G_{12} , while the differences between predicted results and the average values reported by the Boeing company are 0.7% for the in-plane Young's moduli E_1 and E_2 ,

14% for the in-plane Poisson's ratio ν_{12} and 8% for the in-plane shear modulus G_{12} . Thus it is noted that the predicted mechanical properties for a T300/934 plain weave unit cell are generally in good agreement with the present experimental results and those obtained by the Boeing company. However, the FEA results tend to be lower than the measured mechanical properties. One reason for this could be that equation (1) may underestimate the overall fibre volume fraction.

Table 4: Mechanical properties of constituents and impregnated tow for T300/934 composite materials

Item	Material	E_1^* (GPa)	E_2^* (= E_3^*) (GPa)	G_{12}^* (= G_{13}^*) (GPa)	G_{23}^* (GPa)	ν_{12}^* (= ν_{13}^*)	ν_{23}^*
Fibre	(T300)	220	13.8	11.35	5.5	0.2	0.25
Matrix	Epoxy resin (934)	4.1	4.1	1.454	1.454	0.41	0.41
Impregnated tow	(T300/934)	173.11	10.84	6.361	4.165	0.2456	0.3019

* Subscripts 1, 2 and 3 indicate the quantities in longitudinal, transverse and through-the-thickness directions respectively.

Table 5: The comparisons of the mechanical properties for T300/943 plain weave composites

Item	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	E_3 (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)
FEA model $V_f^o=50.1\%$	56.5	56.5	10.18	0.043	0.45	0.45	4.28	2.86	2.86
Test	59.4	59.4	N/A	0.049	N/A	N/A	4.353	N/A	N/A
NASA [25]	53.09- 60.67	53.09- 60.67		0.05			3.1- 6.205		

PARAMETRIC STUDY

Four unit cell models with different geometrical dimensions were developed for the plain weave composite, and they are referred as ModA, ModB, ModC and ModD. Based on the results of these models, the effects of some geometrical parameters on the mechanical properties were discussed. The mechanical properties predicted from model ModA will be compared with those available in the literature.

In all calculations in this section, the overall fibre volume fractions for all four models were chosen to be the same and equal to 58.46%. The relevant geometrical dimensions of unit cells are given in Table 6, in which l_x , l_y and l_z are the length, width and thickness of a unit cell (see Fig. 1).

Table 6: Geometrical parameters for all four models

models	l_x (mm)	l_y (mm)	l_z (mm)
ModA	2.1	2.1	0.19
ModB	2.8	2.8	0.19
ModC	2.1	2.1	0.25
ModC	3	1.5	0.19

Table 7: Mechanical properties of constituents for T300/GY260 composite materials

Material (GPa)	E_1	E_2 (=E ₃)	ν_{12} (=ν ₁₃)	ν_{23}	G_{12} (=G ₁₃)	G_{23}	V_f (%)
Fibre (T300) [17]	220	13.8	0.2	0.25	11.35.	5.5	58.46
Resin (GY260) [17]	3.252	3.252	0.355	0.355	1.2	1.2	41.54
Impregnated tow (T300/GY260)	202.038	12.134	0.2128	0.2704	8.358	4.776	

Table 7 gives the mechanical properties for the T300 carbon fibre, the GY260 epoxy and the impregnated yarn (T300/GY260). It should be mentioned that each impregnated tow (or yarn) in the plain weave composite material was modelled as a unidirectional prepreg. The mechanical properties of the unidirectional fibre yarn were calculated using equations (2) to (7).

Same strain vectors and boundary conditions were applied for the four unit cell models, and the mechanical properties were then obtained following the same procedure as described in the previous sections. Table 8 presents the mechanical properties for all four plain weave unit cell models.

Table 8: Mechanical properties for all four plain weave models

Model	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	E_3 (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)
ModA	65.68	65.68	8.60	0.032	0.364	0.364	5.23	2.71	2.71
ModB	67.10	67.10	8.60	0.032	0.358	0.358	5.26	2.67	2.67
ModC	63.77	63.77	8.60	0.032	0.371	0.371	5.25	2.76	2.76
ModD	67.32	63.23	8.60	0.032	0.356	0.372	5.25	2.67	2.77

By studying the data listed in the first three rows in Table 8, it is noted that when the unit cell dimensions increase in both the warp (x) and the weft (y) directions or decreases in the z direction, the in-plane Young's moduli E_1 , E_2 increase, while the out-of-plane Poisson's ratios ν_{13} , ν_{23} and the shear moduli G_{13} , G_{23} decrease. The variations of dimensions in all three directions almost do not affect the out-of-plane Young's modulus E_3 , the in-plane Poisson's ratio ν_{12} , and the shear modulus G_{12} . For model ModD, the in-plane Young's modulus in the warp direction (ie. with longer unit cell dimension) E_1 is greater than that in the weft direction (ie. with shorter unit cell dimension) E_2 , the out-of-plane Poisson's ratio ν_{23} and shear modulus G_{23} are larger than ν_{13} and G_{13} respectively. It is believed that variations of fibre

orientation could be an important contributing factor to these changes in mechanical properties.

The mechanical properties for model ModA can be compared with those given in Ref. [17], as model ModA was established based on the same geometry reported in Ref. [17]. Table 9 lists the mechanical properties predicted by the present model, and those predicted and measured in Ref. [17]. It is noted that the in-plane Young's modulus E_1 and E_2 obtained from ModA are close to the experimental results and those evaluated from UB's models. The differences between the results of model ModA and the experimental ones are less than 2% for the in-plane Young's modulus E_1 (or E_2). However, the differences for the in-plane Poisson's ratio and the shear modulus are 34% and 20% respectively.

Table 9: Comparison of Mechanical properties between presented and those in Ref [17]

Item	ModA	LB-1 [17]	LB-2 [17]	UB-1 [17]	UB-2 [17]	Test [17]
E_1 (GPa)	65.68	42.97	55.71	67.35	66.44	66.12
E_2 (GPa)	65.68	42.97	55.71	67.35	66.44	66.84
E_3 (GPa)	8.58	8.41	8.44	8.44	8.50	N/A
G_{12} (GPa)	5.23	3.996	N/C	3.98	N/C	4.357
G_{13} (GPa)	2.71	N/C	N/C	N/C	N/C	N/A
G_{23} (GPa)	2.71	N/C	N/C	N/C	N/C	N/A
ν_{12}	0.032	0.323	0.150	0.027	0.0299	0.0476
ν_{13}	0.364	0.257	0.323	0.38	0.4101	N/A
ν_{23}	0.364	0.257	0.323	0.38	0.4101	N/A

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a 3D FEA modelling approach for predicting the mechanical properties of plain weave fabric composites. The present modelling approach was validated by comparing the predicted results with the experimental ones. This modelling approach can be used to model various plain weave composite materials with different geometrical parameters and mechanical properties of composite constituents. The parametric study demonstrated that some mechanical properties, eg, E_1 and E_2 , ν_{13} and ν_{23} , G_{13} and G_{23} are sensitive to the changes in dimensions of a unit cell while others, eg, G_{12} , ν_{12} , and E_3 , are less sensitive or not sensitive.

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